

Madani: Jurnal Ilmiah Multidisiplin

Volume 1, Nomor 6, Juli 2023

E-ISSN: 2986-6340

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8131509>

The Effect of Phonological Abilities for Children in Communication

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Abstract

This research entitled "The Effect of phonological abilities for children in Communication". The purpose of this study was to examine the impact of children's phonological skills on communication. The purpose of this study is to describe children's language acquisition in terms of phonology, including the acquisition of vowels and consonants, and the factors that influence phonological acquisition in communication. The study data are conversations between subjects and their mothers, grandmothers, and other family members and the community. Data collection techniques were performed using recording techniques, notes, and Google Forms. We then analyze the data obtained and use them to conclude stages of language acquisition at the phonological, syntactic, semantic and pragmatic levels.

Keywords: *Effect, Phonology, Children, Communication.*

Abstrak

Penelitian ini berjudul "Pengaruh Keterampilan Fonologis Anak Anak terhadap Komunikasi". Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mengetahui pengaruh keterampilan fonologis anak terhadap komunikasi. Tujuan dari penelitian ini adalah untuk mendeskripsikan pembelajaran bahasa anak dari perspektif fonologis, meliputi pemerolehan vokal, pemerolehan konsonan dan faktor-faktor yang mempengaruhi pemerolehan fonologis dalam komunikasi. Materi penelitian berupa percakapan subjek dengan ibu, nenek dan anggota keluarga lain serta masyarakat. Teknik pengumpulan data dilakukan dengan menggunakan teknik rekam, catatan dan google form. Kemudian kami menganalisis data yang diperoleh dan memutuskan tahapan pemerolehan bahasa pada tingkat fonologi, sintaksis, semantik, dan pragmatik.

Kata Kunci: *Efek, Fonologis, Komunikasi.*

INTRODUCTION

Definition of Phonology is the study of sound patterns within and across languages. More formally, phonology studies the categorical organization of sounds in language. How sounds are constructed in your head and used to convey meaning and Phonological awareness is understanding the different ways that spoken language can be broken down into smaller, more manipulable components. (Chard & Dickson, 1999) More precisely, phonological awareness refers to the more pronounced "chunks" or "parts". of speech. For example, instructing students to rhyme, combine short words into compound words, divide words into syllables, and work at the phonological awareness level.

Phonological awareness can be thought of as his one big umbrella with the more prominent "part of speech" at the top. It is the sound structure of spoken language. This comprehensive ability includes hearing and reproducing small sounds of speech. Phonological awareness involves recognizing and manipulating sounds. This may involve rhyming words, tapping syllables in words, or recognizing the initial sound of words (Morris, 2012). Phonological knowledge predicts future language and reading skills. (NELP, 2010).

Children's sound recognition starts with whole words, then they begin to understand smaller sound units such as syllables, onsets, rhymes and phonemes. (Schickedanz & Collins, 2013) and syllables are the parts of words, or the largest sound units of spoken language. These are uninterrupted sections of speech, usually distinguished by the vowels produced when the word is pronounced. Onset is the first phonological unit of a word. Speech-language pathologists often refer to phonological data norms as part of their assessment protocols when assessing preschoolers' communication skills. Various norms exist, and while they are broadly similar, they differ in the definition of system proficiency for adults.

METHOD

The method used in the research this is a qualitative method with approach case study. Through the observation results of this qualitative method will described acquisition and development Phonology in Children in Communicating.

The data source for this research is through the results of observational data through interviews and the Google form fillers given by the author to several adults, such as family members; parents, brothers, sisters and the community; tutoring teacher.

As we know in daily life, if a child has said a word in a certain communication situation and understood its meaning by the interlocutor, its meaning that the child has mastered the sounds of language the. Furthermore, the data that has been obtained, classified by acquisition group phonology and associated with the views of experts which states that language acquisition following a process that is the opposite of something that easy to more difficult, so every children basically acquire the elements language by following the gradation of difficulty.

Besides In addition, this child is also often invited to the family if there is a family event and to his mother's place teaching, so input development Language acquisition is quite varied. For analysis and comparison with normative data, children were grouped into three age groups according to the age of entry into the study (2-3 years, 3-4 years and 4-5 years). Findings showed similarity in expressiveness among children whose stuttering persisted rather than decreased across age groups. In addition, persistent and recovered stutterers had expressive language skills that were close to or better than developmental expectations compared to normative data across all age groups. Children who participated in the study at the youngest ages consistently demonstrated normative expectations for expressiveness; this pattern was observed in both persistent and recovered groups. These findings provide relatively little information to distinguish between persistence and recovery of early stuttering, but they illuminate theoretical questions about the nature and nature of early stuttering and possible relationships to language learning. Rime is the string of letters that follow the onset (not all terms have a rime).

LITERATURE REVIEW

According to Bruner in Dahar (2005:106) that language is the key to cognitive development, because language is a means of communication between people. To understand the existing concepts, language is needed. Speaking of language then it will be related with sound problems where the process through one of them through the sensory auditory and according to Lancaster and Pope (1997:4) mental operations applied intalk to change shape or ordersound.

In phonological processing there are three components, namely: (1) Phonological Awareness (Phonological Awareness); (2) Naming Speed (Quick Naming) and (3) Ability Remembering Phonology (Phonological Storage). Each one is developed separately (Wagner, Torgensen & Rashette, 1999).

DISCUSSION

One of the existing components in phonological processing is phonological awareness (phonological Awareness). According to Torgesen and Wagner (1998) Phonological Awareness is limited sensitivity or awareness someone with abilities see, think or manipulate the sound structure of the inner words the language. When you see understanding phonological and phonological awareness processing has a study that the same is the problem of sound. phonological awareness is a part of phonological processing like that put forward (Wagner, Torgesen & Rashette, 1999).

Therefore discussion of phonology processing can also use the term phonological awareness. In There are several phonological awareness components include phoneme components, morpheme, semantics, syntax, procedure and pragmatic. Phonological Ability Consciousness is a mental process applied in speech to change sound or order. This will be related with one's abilities in understanding the language components. Mastery of language components includes: (1) shape; (2) morpheme; (3) semantics; (4) syntax; (5) procedures and (6) pragmatics.

“Phonological awareness is about understanding the different ways in which spoken language can be broken down into smaller, more manipulable components.” (Chard & Dickson, 1999) It refers to a “lump” or “part” of a product. "" in language. For example, instructing students to rhyme, combine short words into compound words, divide words into syllables, and work at the phonological awareness level.

Phonological awareness can be thought of as his one big umbrella with the more prominent "parts of speech" at the top. It is the sound structure of spoken language. This comprehensive ability includes hearing and reproducing small sounds of speech. Phonological awareness involves recognizing and manipulating sounds. This may involve rhyming words, tapping syllables in words, or recognizing the initial sound of words (Morris, 2012). Phonological knowledge predicts future language and reading skills. (NELP, 2010). Children's sound recognition starts with whole words, then they begin to understand smaller sound units such as syllables, onsets, rhymes and phonemes. (Sickdanz & Collins, 2013)

A review of the literature reveals that studies into the phonological abilities of children who stutter (e.g. Paden & Yairi, 1996; Paden, Yairi, & Ambrose, 1999) found which of the following:

- a) Persistent and recovered children performed (phonologically) similarly near onset, but the persistent children worsened over time.
- b) Persistent children started out more delayed, but eventually caught up with the recovered children in terms of phonological ability.
- c) Recovered children started out more delayed, but eventually caught up with the persistent children in terms of phonological ability

A syllable is a part of a word, or the largest sound unit in spoken language. These are unbroken sections of speech, usually distinguished by the vowel sounds produced when the word is pronounced. Onset is the first phonological unit of a word. A lime is a sequence of letters following an opening (not all terms have a lime).

What are some signs that children are struggling with phonological recognition? Children develop phonological awareness at different levels. However, some signs may indicate that children are having trouble making ends meet and need additional help. Problems with these skills may indicate reading comprehension problems. Let's see what challenges they face. Difficulties elementary school students may face:

- a) learn nursery rhymes
- b) count syllables in a word
- c) Noticing repeated sounds (alliteration)
- d) Challenges for elementary school students include:

- e) identify the first sound heard in a word
- f) combine individual sounds into words
- g) Invent words that rhyme with wordplay

To read and write words, children need to develop phonological awareness. This helps us understand that words are made up of phonemes, that words have syllables, and how words change when these phonetic parts change. Children cannot read or write without understanding that every word is made up of different sounds (phonemes) and each phoneme represents a different letter. This will help you understand phonetics, phonetics and spelling. Difficulties associated with phonological recognition can be precursors to reading and language impairments. According to Dr. David Kilpatrick, students with strong phonological awareness are good readers. Students with poor phonological awareness have difficulty reading. As mentioned earlier, phonological awareness is a key requirement for reading and writing skills because it teaches people about the sounds that make up words and how they come together to create meaning. Phonological awareness is important precisely because:

- 1) Read and write: Phonological awareness is an integral part of the developmental process of reading and writing. Teach young people the letter-sound relationships they need to learn to read and write.
- 2) Vocabulary Acquisition: Phonological awareness also helps with vocabulary growth. Recognizing and correcting individual sounds helps children better understand and remember new words.
- 3) Speech generation: Phonological recognition is also useful for speech generation. By identifying specific phrases, individuals can speak more accurately and fluently.
- 4) Learn another language: Anyone learning another language should be aware of phonology. This helps children improve their ability to understand and create new sounds and communicate effectively. Needless to say, phonological awareness is essential for improving literacy and communicating effectively. Essential for all ages and very effective

CONCLUSION

First, the acquisition of children's language In addition to physical factors are also determined by stimulation from family and environment. Therefore, for people parents who want their child's language acquisition to be appropriate with physical development, even exceeded should always be given a stimulus by parents and environment. Therefore, the influence factor external plays an important role. Second, this research is still wide open done by other researchers, because Each child's language acquisition is unique each. In addition, the research aspect Children's language acquisition also varies, namely from aspects of phonology, syntax, morphology, semantics, and etc.

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